

Open Access Software Usage in Public and Private Institutions: Existing Legislation and New Challenges in SE Europe

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Abstract

The last three decades have been marked by a series of fundamental discoveries in the field of informatics, that lead to the development of a new vast sector, called information technology, IT. This sector, that is including both software and hardware, has become an integrated part of every day life. It is applicable both in private life, private activities and business, but also in the public, political and educational institutions among others. This study is examining the initial stages of development of software and its legal framework related to intellectual property legislation, but also new forms of software, that are called open source. More specifically the new legal environment and the challenges in south East Europe are studied, with all the characteristics deriving from historical and social factors. The scope of this paper is the current financial conditions and the necessity for new, more economical, efficient and accessible instruments.

Keywords

Software, Intellectual Property, Open Access, Open Source, Creative Commons

Introduction

Charles Babbage, an English mechanical engineer and polymath, conceived the concept of a programmable computer. Considered the "father of computing", he conceptualized and invented the first mechanical computer in the early 19th century, in 1837 (Fuegi, 2003). After the end of Second World War computers have been produced and developed massively and extensively mainly in United States of America. A milestone took place in 1969 by the decision to separate software and hardware. This bold move forwarded by IBM initiated a totally new era. Within a very short period of time computers became smaller and their software faster due to synergies in research and development. The separation of software also created a separate market that had to be regulated, a vast market with high potential. In the beginning, software was sold like any other publication. Gradually it was evident that this approach was not adequate to cover a completely new market with significant differences from the book market. New approaches were attempted and one of them was to license software to the public to private and public legal entities. The legal community had to arrive to a consensus regarding the legal nature of the new product and

new rights – obligations. The result of this debate was to adopt the copyright protection, Computers Software Protection Act of 1980, and in EU to follow this path with Directive 91/250/EEC, regulating as well intellectual property for software. Consequently Software is falling under the strict protection of Intellectual Property. A more recent development of Free and Open Software is the Creative Commons license. In this area, as well, the relationship between the user and the creator is defined in its range and value by a common agreement. This legal context is of course influencing both private and public sector to different extent due to the fact that in the intellectual property law during last years there is a tendency to introduce certain elements of public law and public rights. This is applicable not only in Free and Open Software movement or creative commons licenses but also in the creator-centric continental law in Europe but as well in copyright law of USA.

1. Intellectual property (IP) rights

The definition of the Intellectual Property rights concentrates in the exclusive protection of creation of the intellect, the mind. The creator or the holder of those rights, is granted certain intangible rights and the most common of them, are the following: copyright, trademarks, patents, industrial design rights and trade dress among others, indicative and not restrictively. The moral foundations of the protection of Intellectual Property rights is based on the concept of functionality. Labor and the creation of labor are a functional bondage that is always in favor, and working for social progress. In older structures the right was granted as a result of the control of one person over the products of one self. The person has this right as a result of the direction of his or her will. According to Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author. The latest legislation in Greece, in article 2 paragraph 1 of law 2121/93, is defining the notion of creation of the mind of intellectual property as every original creation of the mind, manifested in any form, including an indicative number of mind creations under protection. (Koumantos, et. al., 2014)

2. Conjunction of Intellectual Property with Software

As mentioned before the law of Intellectual Property is not just a legal construction created during last 30 years. The legal concept of Intellectual Property Law has been conceived since the Ancient Years because is consistent with the creation of human intellect. Nevertheless with the Industrial Revolution knowledge and science are becoming technology, and technology is becoming the base of business and then of enterprises. With this transformation, Intellectual Property is acquiring also value in the production chain and is becoming an intangible asset. In parallel to the expansion of the capitalism almost on a global level, with the above scope, Intellectual Property is transcending national borders and is becoming international. On those initial stages the necessity was to protect the individual from any infringement and to

create a protective environment, preventing any external interference, mainly from the state authority. The final recipient of those benefits, was indirectly, the society. So from one side the scope and the protection of Intellectual Property Rights became international. The Convention of Berne in 1886 was the first part of a long chain in a long sequence of treaties that in a sense has created a global protection of Intellectual Property. European Treaty of Geneva in 1952, European Law – Directives 2001/29, 91/250, 96/9 (Kotsiris, 2011), World Trade Organization, 94/800 EC. Also WIPO Copyright Treaty in 1996. (Synodinou, 2008) The long chain of the above mentioned treaties and legislation has created a matrix of strong and almost impervious protection for Intellectual Protection Rights. There are very few exemptions, mainly related to the implementation of the three steps criteria. On the other hand parallel to the creation of protection for Intellectual Property, the focus shifted from the person to other entities. The person has been replaced by huge legal entities of multinational nature transcending local legislation and yielding enormous financial, political and marketing power. This commercial approach also used Intellectual Property as a part of asset, of property subject to trading and valuing. In the last years, also, the recipient of the knowledge, the audience, has changed in nature due to existence of new media. Printing is not anymore the most used way to spread knowledge. Audience, in the way it was known in the past, is there no more. Audience is not any more a passive recipient but the relationship is more and more interactive, due to information technologies. Audience, now in the field of informatics has been replaced by the users. A user is not passive anymore but intensively interactive, exploring, creating, experimenting, commenting, changing and modifying.

3. From Protected Software under Intellectual Property to new form of Software

With the lobbying and the discussions of the legal community arriving to an end, protecting almost completely software with strict Intellectual Property Rights, a reaction ensued. Since the beginning of this course and the introduction of restrictive legislation a new trend emerged, due to the fact that as the value of the market of software was increasing, the more it was regarded as a close held trade secret. Richard M. Stallman, the famous MIT programmer and software freedom activist, considered this direction taken as unacceptable. Richard M. Stallman quit MIT in 1983 and founded what later became the Free Software Foundation. The goal of this foundation is to create and stimulate software available to everybody. Stallman drafted the GNU General Public License or GPL, a software license that allows anyone to freely use, distribute and adapt the licensed software at no charge. In contrast to copyright Stallman's lawyer introduced the term copyleft. Thus the concept of Free and Open Source Software, FOSS, was well established (Engelfriet, 2011). The effort was a huge success. In 1991 a Finnish second year student Linus Torvalds created Linux. Similar concepts were applied by Open Access, OA, which means unrestricted online access to peer reviewed scholarly research. Open Access is primarily intended for scholarly articles (Raysman, 1998). There are two main

separations into gratis OA, which is free online access and libre OA which is free on line access plus additional rights. Licences are issued by the organization Creative Commons, a foundation created by Lawrence Lessing. Creative commons licenses are a compromise between the traditional intellectual property law (all rights reserved), with the free and open source software (no right reserved) coining the term "*some rights reserved*" (Creative Commons, 2001 and Lessing, 2004)

4. Free Open Software, OA, Creative Commons And Developing Countries

According to the International Monetary Fund the definition of a country as developing is based on lower living standard, under developed industrial base and a low Human Development Index, or HDI, relative to other countries. The question that is arising revolves around the possibilities to decrease and bridge the gap. Unless new natural resources are discovered one of the most secure way to succeed in this is the enhancement of learning. The creation of capable workforce is the best path forward. Of course this process should be achieved in parallel to the development of more developed countries. Learning is not only achieved by the traditional methods but also with media like internet, movies, music and other elements that constitute the so called cultural assimilation. This process is not always negative but is creating the same level of understanding and awareness among people of developed and less developed countries. On the other hand corruption in the less developed countries could lead to misuse of resources. The institution of open government and similar methods of e-publications could lead to decrease of corruption. Less corruption could lead to faster development because more resources would be available (Suber, 2004).

5. Developments in Balkans, an example in the field of open source usage in developing countries

In that frame we could detect that similar activities to above mentioned process are taking places all over Balkans as well. In Kosovo there is an annual Software Conference, SFK, for promoting FOSS. This conference is organized by Free/Libre Open Source Software Kosova (FLOSSK, 2012), Kosovo Association of Information and Communication Technology, IPKO Foundation and Faculty of Electrical and Computer Engineering of the University of Prishtina. Internet Society Bulgaria (2004) promoting an initiative based on Free/Open Source Software, FOSS, at the local (municipality) level in the Southern- Eastern Europe. In nine municipalities in the region, Bulgaria – Kardjali, Vratza, Mezdra, Peshtera, Belovo, Dryanovo Kostenetz, FYROM Gevgelija, Kosovo – Klina. Open Office and Mozilla Firefox were installed in 200 workstations. Linux was installed in 45 work stations. Benefits and impacts are studied while lessons learned are evaluated.

Conclusions and Proposals

Software in computers, in hardware, is essential in most, if not in all, sectors of our every day life. This is applicable both in Public and Private Sector as well. Economy, Education, Politics and Administration are operating through computers and their software. Software though is mainly produced and marketed in developed countries, while the source code is protected by Intellectual Property Law rights now are able to be enforced all over the world. Legal rights that were developed in a period where the protection of the individual was necessary from the state oppression, must now be addressed under completely different conditions. Those conditions are not applicable anymore because the holders of those rights are multinational corporations yielding enormous power and commanding vast pool of resources.

The restrictions in the spread of knowledge and information is creating a gap between developed and less developed countries. The demand of royalties is intensifying this unequal conditions leaving less developed countries in poverty, corruption and limited accessibility to education. This situation is more acute nowadays due to the crisis of the economy that is spread all over the world due to unrestricted usage of complicated financial instruments.

Reactions to the above described inequality have been coming from the same origins of software developers. Reactions came from the same people that contributed to this tremendous explosion of creation in this sector. Many programmers decided to distribute their software for free. This phenomenon caused the development of the open source software and the creation commons. As we have seen, this trend is allowing less developed countries to take advantage of the new systems of organization in administration, preventing corruption and promoting democracy thus increasing the standard of life. Also the same is achieved in Universities, where much needed funding is not dedicated to royalties but can be used in other more efficient purposes.

From the point of legal discussion in the end it is obvious that the current structure is extremely restrictive towards reducing the Intellectual Protection Rights over software. The arguments in favor should be weighted together with public interest and the necessity of creating a more just and equal international environment, thus reducing frictions.

A discussion should start with arguments from Constitutional Law, Public Law and from International Law. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights and a broader vision of the Legal under-structure can give arguments to allow more exemptions of Intellectual Property Rights than the exemptions recognized with the three criteria process. Indeed the argument that digital is different can be accepted but in favor of liberty and not of restriction. Exemptions could be accepted towards sectors where resources are needed, i.e. education or public administration of developing countries, and there are methods available to monitor that those exemptions will not lead to infringement of Intellectual Property.

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